
EVOLUTION OF FINANCIAL MECHANISMS OF STATE REGULATION AND MANAGEMENT INSTRUMENTS IN INFRASTRUCTURE SUPPORT FOR THE INTERACTION OF SMALL AND MEDIUM BUSINESSES AND HIGHER EDUCATION

This article examines the theoretical and institutional foundations of interaction between small and medium-sized businesses and higher education, the specifics of its government regulation, and the importance of infrastructure support for achieving national development goals, including accelerated income growth for SME employees. The authors conduct a retrospective analysis of the evolution of state policy in the SME sphere, examine the dynamics of legal and regulatory frameworks, demonstrate the structure of SME demand for support measures, and analyze the financial instruments used at various stages of the development of the institution of entrepreneurship support. A rationale for the need to develop a comprehensive organizational and managerial mechanism for infrastructure support of interaction between SMEs and higher education, including the institutional, functional, technological, and financial levels, is presented. A systemic gap is identified consisting of the lack of targeted funding for cooperation between businesses and universities within the existing support infrastructure, despite the predominance of educational and consulting requests from the business community. The proposed mechanism allows for the integration of higher education into the SME support system as a strategic partner and creates conditions for increasing the budgetary efficiency of expenditures on human resource development.

Keywords: small and medium-sized businesses, higher education, infrastructure support, government regulation, financial support mechanisms, transaction costs, interaction management, digital transformation, human resources, budget efficiency.

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